

Interview transcript STE *Localisation and decentralisation*

Interview date: 24.04.2023

Participants: P8, P9

I [00:00:04] Yep. Okay. Nice. Nice to see you. And so, yeah, I think we're all. So welcome. Thank you very much for your time and to participate in this interview. So before we start. So you already you both already sent me the declaration of consent for the interview. So for the recording, are there any questions regarding this, Any doubts issues, or is everything clear?

P8 [00:00:35] Not for the moment.

P9 [00:00:38] Okay. For me, it's also clear. Yeah.

I [00:00:41] Sounds very good. Okay, so then I will start the recording. Yeah. So, yeah, briefly about the course and the duration of the interview. So I planned and totally one and a half hours. And so I will start or we will start with an introduction round and I will explain the goals and the methodology of the interview. And this will take around 15 minutes and then we will have around 60 minutes or an hour for the concrete interview itself and in the end, 15 minutes again for reflection and a little feedback round. And does it work for you or do you have any time constraints?

P9 [00:01:24] For me. It's fine. An hour and a half? No. No time constraints.

P8 [00:01:28] Sounds really good for me. Preferably a lot longer. Yeah.

I [00:01:33] Okay. Yeah. I tried to keep it in, like, the one and a half hours. So nice. Okay. So, yeah, I will maybe quickly introduce myself. And so I'm I [interviewer]. I'm a student at the University of Osnabrück, and I'm currently writing my master's thesis in collaboration with Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research. That's how I got in touch with you. And the topic of my thesis is about social tipping, tipping elements for transitioning to regenerative agriculture. Yeah, and so my personal link to agriculture, regenerative agriculture. So I've been always interested in social processes and environmental processes similarly. So agriculture kind of represented a perfect fit for me because I could do both in a way. And I think that also, yeah, regenerative agriculture or agriculture in general has or can have a huge impact or can be the solution of many problems that we currently facing, such as climate change or biodiversity crisis. So that's why I focused on that topic. Um, yeah. And now I would like to ask you to quickly introduce yourself maybe with your name and your professional background and your personal or professional relation to regenerative agriculture. Um, I don't know who wants to start.

P8 [00:03:03] Please go ahead.

P9 [00:03:05] Yeah, right. Good. Um, yeah. So why am I here today? PERSONAL INFORMATION. So really a strong believer of if you know, the tipping point, you can work on all of them. So I'm really glad that you continue with this because I think it's it's worth to have more research done. So I'm very happy about that. I used to work as a consultant and a strategy advisor and an executive team coach for a long time for almost, I think 20, 22, 22 years. And I worked for the big multinationals like ORGANISATIONS and all the big ones. So did that for a long time. And then I started to realize more and more that in my private life I was looking at documentaries like Kiss the Ground and lots of other things. And then I decided to stop with my old profession and to to have time to to study and to network and find out what to do next. And that was, I think, two years ago. And I'm still in the middle of exploration, but I've worked with ORGANISATION. It's a Dutch word. I don't know if you speak any Dutch, but ORGANISATION is is an organisation where they grow grains like wheat and other (incomprehensive - Dutch expression), which are typically Dutch together with the flowers in the fields. And therefore we enhance biodiversity and we enhance the water in the grounds and lots of things. And we don't use, of course, any pesticides and no, no, no artificial manure. So that's what I've done for a while. And now I'm also involved with the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) [Dutch name of an organisation], which is an organisation for sustainability in Holland. And I work with ORGANISATION, which is a (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) and they do research for wealth and not for multinationals, but to really find climate justice and to find the things that are going wrong, which is also very interesting. But it's not really building on something. It's really making sure we have the data about things that go wrong.

I [00:05:37] Okay, Thank you.

P8 [00:05:43] Though I am P8, also living in the Netherlands. So you too I think P9. So I was also there at the Earth Day last year, but didn't manage this year. I've actually worked at ORGANISATION for 17 years and it's a company that started their transformation towards a more sustainable company already back in the nineties and they embrace biomimicry learning from nature. So when I joined them in 2003, I got to learn that together with this yes, science or approach in combination with the natural step, which is a framework for strategic sustainable development. As they have already for ten years on the journey, but I wasn't there, I've been growing and developing both the company and myself at the same time when working with them. And then we were challenged [?] By Paul Hawken, the man that challenged [?] already back in the nineties to take the next step. Actually at that time, based on his project Drawdown, which was focusing on radical CO2 reduction. But when you looked at the solutions, they were all, yeah, actually addressing multiple sustainable development goals. So really holistic approach. So we took, we decided that we had to go beyond.

I always say, like learning instead of learning from nature to functioning as nature, which is a more regenerative approach and actually ORGANISATION is now a process on finding ways how to do that as a company with factories that functions as a forest. So two years ago I was like, you know, I'm actually now we have we are on a new path, a new mountain. And I've experienced a struggle, you know, where you don't know exactly how it's going to work out, which I didn't experience in the 1990s, so I could stay for another seven years easily. But I was like, I'm curious, was come to my path and I really wanted to focus on bringing sustainability with a focus on regeneration further with other organisations as well. So actually I don't have a particular knowledge in regeneration, but I do have experience in engaging people and in both individuals and organisations into sustainability. So and I think a more local approach is crucial for everything.

I [00:08:18] So yeah, perfect. Yeah, Thank you a lot. And so now I can quickly explain the goals again of the interview and the methodology. So in the workshop last year, um like, you collected a lot of interventions in different areas. I don't know if you're that's also how you know, and ended up in localisation and decentralisation. But for example, there were other areas such as education, finance and law and policy and for the social, so we call them social tipping elements. And for us, for the social tipping element of localisation and decentralisation, for me, it's kind of hard to to define this because it's not like I think it came up during the workshops or just before the workshops. And so my first questions to you would be what do what you understand? Yeah, under localisation and decentralisation. So what? Why is it a social tipping element? Why is it important? Yeah, that would be my first question.

P8 [00:09:28] Okay. You want us to respond right now?

I [00:09:30] Yes.

P8 [00:09:31] Yeah, yeah, yeah. I really appreciated this field of work of Daniel Wahl which has done a lot on what he calls Oh I don't know. (incomprehensive expression), if I pronounce it correctly, but how I like to explain it, is that, you know, we always think with scaling that we have to scale up, but you just need. You can also scale in a farm in a more distributive way. I think, for example, the Seaweed Company [<https://www.theseaweedcompany.com/>] is a great example. You know, they are growing sea weed and not trying to grow as much as possible in one place. But really look at the place, what are the possibilities here, how large can we go without causing any problems and what listed type of sea wheat we should we should grow here and yeah, really actively duplicate the model in areas and adjusting it in in their way, in the to the place where they are working here which I also have learned doing my biomimicry study and the genius of place and take that into account and it's actually also account for people. I would I would say a lot of the issues I think there are is because of scale, because we overdo, too big, too large, too much. And I think scaling in another way is really,

really crucial and also far more engaging. And it doesn't mean that you don't can't connect with it in a more global perspective, which it has to be. Yeah, this, although smaller, helps, and then you can connect in a more regional way or maybe even eventually even also in a global way, but the basis should be a smaller scale. I believe even the book of Malcolm Gladwell, if you talk about a tipping point, there's this example, you know that up to 500 people that works for community and then it actually already becomes too large. Now that is an example. We just need to organize ourselves on a far more smaller scale. So that's why I liked it.

I [00:11:41] Okay.

P8 [00:11:41] And there are a lot of examples. P9 already mentioned one, which are in the Netherlands, like Herenboeren [<https://www.herenboeren.nl/>] or FoodsAmabssador [? - Dutch name of an initiative]. There are so many initiatives. And of course the argument that is always used is there won't be enough to feed the world. I don't agree because we don't have to feed to feed the world from the Netherlands. You know, you just have to help everyone to feed themselves in their own environment. And then it can perfectly work.

I [00:12:09] Nice okay.

P8 [00:12:10] According to my opinion, not being not being an experts.

I [00:12:14] Yeah. I mean, that's what we are looking at here.

P8 [00:12:18] Yeah.

P9 [00:12:20] Yeah, I can just fully second all that you've said basically, and I think very interesting. From my background, I came from Business administration studies in Master and I was a consultant, all these large organisations. And I think they're also struggling on the inside because it's not very healthy, I think, to be in a big office space all the time, not being in touch with nature. Just so also from a social innovation perspective, I don't think it's it's good the way we live. I don't believe it's it's healthy. And I think the power of these large organisations is is way too big. So also something needs to happen there to really break down that power again. And it's can only be done by local organisations that become bigger and bigger, but not as big that they have to rule the world, but just big enough to feed their local community and work with their local community. And I have a good friend and she's working on retail and and she's like a manager of a shopping area. And and she has these same examples there. Like in Paris, they have this 10 minutes local organisational principle, and they kind of try to have everything within a ten minute bicycle ride like a doctor and the food and the school and the nature. So I think in many ways, we are trying to reinvent ourselves.

Well, in my heart goes to the the agricultural part of it. I don't exactly know why, but I think it's just really interesting. But I think it's much more white energy. Everything we do could be done much more local without ignoring global knowledge. So I do agree with that P8. You can use regional knowledge and local knowledge and yeah, and I think if we're talking about books I'm reading at the moment. Charles Eisenstein So the whole the whole concept of how do we live and what are we thriving for? I think if we can make that change slowly but surely people understand we are in a, uh, in a new era and we can think differently and then act differently. I think a lot can can be changed.

I [00:14:45] Yeah thank you a lot I mean that help me really to, to understand it a bit more actually. So perhaps I will ask you in the end again to send me the names of the authors and just the names you just said, because I I'm sure if I can. Um. So I tried to, to write it down a bit, but I think it didn't capture everything.

P9 [00:15:07] I'm not sure if I can mention it later, but so I mentioned it now maybe. What I did experience a lot of difficulty to reinstate local supply chains. For instance, with Hachnelook [?] Because there are very practical things like there are not enough production, local production facilities to have the grains produced. So. So there's there's still a lot of work that needs to be done to make it all local. So that takes that does take a lot of effort in one.

I [00:15:38] Yeah, Yeah. So keep that in mind. I think we will have the chance to add it somehow to the interview later.

P9 [00:15:46] Yeah.

I [00:15:47] Um, yeah. Great. So. Yeah. So going back to the interview. So the goal is really to find the interventions that are needed for establishing conditions to transition to regenerative agriculture. And it might be clearer later. And I know that there are a lot of different definitions of regenerative agriculture and that, yeah, you can define it really narrow, but also quite broad. So I just choose the definition and I will send it in the chat. And yeah, if you have like huge objections, of course we can discuss it, but otherwise I would just leave it like it is and continue if that's okay for you. But I would quickly send it in the chat so you could have read.

P9 [00:16:40] Is it different I, from the definition we used last year in.

I [00:16:45] Oh actually I am not sure which definition you used last year because I was not completely involved in the in the workshops last year. So I just took a quite popular definition that is used in research.

P9 [00:17:12] I have no objections. I mean, no.

P8 [00:17:15] No, I don't understand actually the uses. Soil conservation is the entry point.

I [00:17:22] So I think that so I understand it, as it that it's the basis of some of the practices and things like this are related to.

P8 [00:17:30] Because I would say that uses soil regeneration, as an entry, as the as the principal. So that's. You know, Yeah. So that's, that's maybe more the way in that it's formulated, Yeah. Now I'm okay. I have no objection.

P9 [00:17:44] But I can relate, like enhancement of the soil, it doesn't necessarily just mean conserve it the way it is, enriches it or.

P8 [00:17:54] Yeah yeah it's often and that's the point. It's not uh, the state as is, is, is, is, is quite narrow.

I [00:18:05] And that's often what.

P9 [00:18:06] The conservation is not enough.

I [00:18:09] Yeah.

P8 [00:18:10] Yeah. Which is follow out then in the following sentences, but therefore it just doesn't make sense.

I [00:18:15] Yeah, I keep it in mind.

P9 [00:18:18] It's ok. I think we are, we have a common understanding.

I [00:18:22] Okay, perfect. So yeah, the outputs of this interview will be, again, like maps or diagrams like last year, if you remember. And I will use these diagrams to analyse the effects of different interventions. And my goal is also to combine the diagrams of different social tipping elements. So in the end, combine, for example, localisation and decentralisation with information feedbacks. And so I plan to make like more bigger diagrams, but interviews are focusing on smaller diagrams. So I will share my screen now to show you the diagram. Um. Mhm. And probably it's quite small at the moment but you can make it bigger. Just put it on full screen and just leave your own microphone on so you don't have to switch all the time. And so yeah. Maybe to quickly explain you the interview

set up. So I decided to organize the elements in three categories. Um, so there are interventions which are really mainly elements that were mentioned during the workshop last year. Um, and then there are conditions. So these are elements I also extracted from the workshop last year, but also from literature. And these are really elements that are considered to enable the social tipping to happen, so enable the transition to regenerative agriculture to happen and to make maybe the difference between interventions and conditions a bit more explicit. So yeah, conditions are elements that really need to be fulfilled so that the transition in process can happen. For example, the public knowledge or awareness of regenerative agriculture needs to increase, and interventions are elements that trigger processes that help to fulfil these conditions. For example, information campaigns. So information campaigns can help that public knowledge can increase. So that's kind of the differentiation between these two. And lastly, there are also consequences and consequences is everything that results or that happens if these conditions are met. It might also be that the consequences influence other social tipping elements, for example, education. And as you see, there are already three elements which were mentioned last year and for the interviews. So we will go through these three categories step by step, but we will also look at all of them together. And, and in the workshop last year, you like you collected a lot of elements and I would really like to focus on the interconnections between these elements. But of course, it's also possible to add new elements or to delete elements if you think they're not necessary and sometimes also necessary to to add an element to establish a connection. But yeah focus is a little bit on our is should be on the interconnections between the elements and not only between the categories, but also within the categories. And to create these interconnections, I would like to follow a certain notion guideline, which is drawn here. So an arrow means that one element influences another element, and there are two kinds of errors. So there are positive errors and negative errors. And the positive arrows mean that the two elements change in the same direction. So if A increases, B increases, and if A decreases B decreases, and if we have a negative error, that means that these two elements change in different directions. So if A increases, B decreases and if A decreases B increases. So if we look at an example, for example, yeah, if the public knowledge or awareness of regenerative agriculture increases, we could assume that also more people recognize values for nature, agriculture and food. And so that's the general general idea behind these arrows. And for the interviews idea is really that the the two of you discuss with each other. And I would rather map and we try to connect everything in the end. So yeah, that's the idea. Do you have any questions regarding this?

P8 [00:23:31] I made it a little bit bigger, but in I don't see you, so.

I [00:23:35] I mean, I'm not like. The map is more important. So if you need to make it bigger and you don't see me anymore. It's. It's okay. Yeah. And I will also give.

P9 [00:23:49] And I? You don't want us to come up with new things. So first we focus on things that are on here and then try to connect it and, and if they pop up.

I [00:23:59] So if you have new things that are important, of course add them. So because in the workshop last year, there were a lot of a lot of elements that were mentioned and I had to reduce them a little bit and I hope I didn't delete it an important one, but if it happened, of course add it or if you think of something new, which is important aslo also add it. Um.

P9 [00:24:20] Yeah.

I [00:24:21] Yeah. Okay, So if there are not any questions regarding the methodology, I would give you maybe, I don't know, two or 3 minutes now to read through the elements that are already there and just to get familiar with them and so we can clarify any questions or if any terms are not clear. Um, yeah. Can you read everything? More or less? Or should I?

P9 [00:24:47] Yes.

P8 [00:24:48] Yes. Okay. If I, I've enlarged the presentation.

I [00:24:53] Okay. Yeah. I'm sorry. I mean, with Zoom actually it would have been a little bit easier, but. Yeah, like this.

P9 [00:25:04] Only the top one. I can't read. Yeah. Now I can see it again. Okay.

I [00:25:09] Okay. Nice.

P9 [00:25:35] One question. The green ones. Yeah. Those are the the negative ones I guess.

I [00:25:40] Yeah, yeah. There are kind of anti interventions. I don't know more barriers or. Yeah.

P9 [00:25:51] Yeah. I'm ready to to discuss if you are P8.

P8 [00:26:05] Yeah. Perfect.

I [00:26:07] Okay, So I would like to start with the conditions. So the elements in the middle and here the question is, um. Yeah. What is needed to transition to regenerative agriculture from the perspective of localisation and decentralisation? Um, and what do you think, what are the most

important conditions and are the most important conditions already captured? So if here it's especially relevant, if anything is missing that you add it?

P9 [00:26:39] Yeah, I think I was wondering about purely the availability of the food for people on a local level. Mm hmm. Because most people still go to the supermarket and grab their food there. So I think you still have to kind of investigate and really do your best to find out where to get things. And then you have to go to different places to pick them up. So something about a central local supermarket place would be interesting.

P8 [00:27:20] And that's what I really like about the Herenboeren concepts I, because what they do, I think, it's really very practical. It's not people moving to the countryside. They actually bring the farmer to the people and they ensure. And there are more initiatives, similar same initiatives. But I think I will put the name here, so you'll find it, You know the concept already?

I [00:27:47] I have to. I think I don't know the Dutch organisation.

P8 [00:27:51] What they do. They set up the, uh, they actually involve people in a certain neighbourhood there in the city, in a town that need to be around 100 to 200 families and want to invest in local, local foods creation and growing or farming. And then they actually buy a farm and they actually hire a farmer who does all the work that has and is assured of an income because he already has a the community is paying a certain fee for the food they get so they and children can see where it's growing because it's typically in your own neighbourhood. So, you know, less than four kilometres from where you live. And I really like that practical approach. And I spoke to the initiator, and he said that actually you could even feed the whole Netherlands with this concept. And I believe that that is true. So, you know, and, and therefore, I'm not one that I want to disturb the flow of your interview. But what I'm really worried about is indeed about the counter lobby, because there's this pressure that to farmers you won't be able to to make money if you go that way. Um what happens in the Netherlands with with the provincial elections and sub regional elections. That's that a party which is actually, you know, set up by the huge traditional, uh, and let's say agricultural wholesalers who sell to farmers what they need. They, they won because of their their support, which is, you know, something I felt that can only happens in the US and it just happens in the Netherlands as well. That's where I'm really, really, really worried about. And at the same time, I do see, you know, these kind of initiatives P9 mentioned to a few like Herenboren, even here in a place where I leave, live they are starting an agricultural forest an agri forest. So you know we can take the initiative ourselves. You don't have to wait and change the system. And I think that's from my perspective, the most important thing that we shouldn't try to change the system but really start follow a dilemma [?]. I think it was actually (incomprehensible) [name of a person] who said to, you know, just make

new systems to make the old one obsolete and ghost fighting the old system, it's not going to work and it's going to take too long. And it's just possible, you know, it's happening all around us. So.

I [00:30:58] Yeah, super interesting. Can we try to connect it somehow to the to the existing post-its?

P8 [00:31:07] Yeah, P9 knows how.

P9 [00:31:09] Because I think many things are already in there like connections between farmers and the community, the society on the left bottom. You see that.

I [00:31:19] This one. Yeah.

P9 [00:31:21] Yeah, yeah. That's already, that's about, you know, farmers and the community working together.

I [00:31:27] Yeah.

P9 [00:31:28] So basically local initiatives. Yeah. And the other one is also in their access to local markets for regenerative products. So it is already in here. It's kind of sickening those too.

I [00:31:48] Um, and markets. So this one Okay, I mean the access to local markets from a consumer perspective because.

P9 [00:31:59] Yeah. And, but also for farmers right? That's, that has two angles.

I [00:32:17] Um, yeah, I actually really liked the sentence that you said that not make people move to the countryside, but also brings the farmers to the people, in the cities.

P8 [00:32:29] And it doesn't have to be, you know, vertical farming. And that can be as well. So it can be the roofs of what you see happening of course, in cities, but there is enough space to integrate, especially with like example of agri forest approach. Also, Herenboeren is developing themselves further because first it was really food, but also they see, you know, we need to go for a better balance in vegetarian and the proteins and and enrich the soil. So also those initiatives are evolving further, but the model itself is really, really can that can work from my opinion.

P9 [00:33:10] Yeah. I totally agree because there's also a farm Bodemzicht [<https://www.bodemzicht.nl/>].

P8 [00:33:16] Yeah. For example.

P9 [00:33:17] Everybody knows them and they're close to the city. It's not like a beautiful farm with a lot of, you know, nature around it. It's just really close to the city. And they started to work the grounds and now it's working. So I think if you have enough farms around cities, you can do a lot and then you might need some vertical farming maybe in Rotterdam or in in Amsterdam. But that's that's fine. You can grow lettuce in a vertical farm, still I would rather eat lettuce from the ground, not from of water. Yeah from from but but then again if it's needed for a for just for for a time. Yeah. Then you can still use that method. It's not harmful at least. I mean you're not using pesticides then you're not using artificial stuff to grow it. So that's already good. Better than the old system. Yeah.

I [00:34:13] So from what you said, I, I tried to highlight the ones I, I felt are really important. So the local initiatives, the connection between farmers and communities, the access to local markets and that like the other post-its that I edit, are not as important. Just maybe for us to, to focus and few.

P8 [00:34:35] To be honest, I think there is too much focus on trying to change the system. The old system, you know, that's yeah, and we got to fix the (Dutch word) in Dutch, so work. That is going too too much time effort you know you just have to win people one by one. And you know if people get into action [?] because that's what I saw for example for example happening with Herenboeren, but also with initiatives like Lenteland [<https://www.lente.land/>] and Bodemzicht maybe relatively still small but, you know, families start to take their children to where the food is grown and they like it and they see some small lams and yeah, and they see how it's growing and indeed they get seasonal foods and and the fresh strawberry berries, which are far more tasty. So it's, it's like also yeah, a social, a social dimension to it and that's the story that starts telling itself and I think those kind of things are important. So you have that in your interventions as well. Actually a whole and but it's not an information again, again, it's actually a narrative, a mean, that it's going to spread itself.

I [00:35:52] So if you if you don't have anything to add for the conditions, we can also move to the interventions. You're already started, but yeah, so with the conditions. Yeah, it's okay?

P9 [00:36:02] Yeah, because I agree. Because then like the the information or the knowledge about it is important. But then I think there was another tipping point that you have to, you know, and farmers can teach farmers and you can bring it to schools, etc.. So I think it's a different tipping point and also land access because of course you do need land, but that's also a different tipping point I think.

P8 [00:36:29] There was something then maybe to bring into the discussion, maybe out of topic. But what I another worry and I'm actually always on the positive side is the energy transition. You know you see in Germany, for example that there is a lot of farms let's say meadows covered with solar panels. Okay, I, I do have an opinion on that. But in Germany I would say there is enough space. If I see this in the Netherlands, I'm I'm getting completely mad. And it's happening in on a scale. It's really ridiculous. There are enough roofs. And then they say, Yeah, but the roofs are not designed for it. Okay. Then you just create a steel structure and you can put it there because all those meadows, they also have steel constructions, only one and half a meter high and then you just have to make the train[?] all the meters high. So what's the problem? But you don't want to know how many solar panels are grown on land. And ok maybe typically that's, of course, not farmland, but meadows or along the highway. But still, we are covering space with something, with something that's easily could be placed somewhere else, not taking additional space. So this space so it is going to be the link with other transitions. I think it's really important. So I'm not sure having it in the conditions yeah it's again just taking a holistic approach not only from an agricultural perspective but actually from what is needed to get from A to B if this is the future.

P9 [00:38:06] Yeah, because we were discussing this also, was it yesterday, yesterday, before on Earth Day, I was again on Hoorneboeg.

P8 [00:38:13] Ah great. I missed it.

P9 [00:38:14] There was from Amsterdam, a guy who who is a regenerative farmer and he says, we're actually looking for land around Amsterdam because it's just hard to find it. We have this group of young farmers and we don't have the money. And so how do we get land? And that of course there were people there that could help like Lenteland and other and other organisations. And at the same time there was another guy and he said, Yeah, well, I live I was in the south of Holland, and now these farmers get money to close their big farms, which is in itself a good thing that they closed down these big farms, but then they get millions from the government to close down. And I'm not sure what happens with these lands could be the case they build.

P8 [00:39:01] Why not use that money? And and how do you say.

P9 [00:39:05] And change it.

P8 [00:39:06] Condition that you have to transform to, hey, maybe if you don't want to do that yourself after having being a pig farming pigs for such a long day, but at least you know that you have to, if you want to sell it, that you need to sell it to someone who is taking this regenerative approach. So I mean, yeah, yeah, yeah.

P9 [00:39:23] These are all older people who have no ancestors in the family that wanted to take the farm, so they actually need to stop their business. And yeah, so we were actually talking about why can't we get a lobby ahead to the governments where we lobby for it? Because that's just a waste of money to give them millions and then they have big cars and they can go on many holidays with that money. Okay, maybe give them some money, but it should be used otherwise. Not like this. Could be used to make the land accessible for younger people who would like to farm there in a regenerative way and not put houses there. Or more industrial boxes for Amazon or DHL. Yeah.

I [00:40:18] I just try to capture this. The same.

P8 [00:40:22] Thing in the boxing.

P9 [00:40:30] Mhm. To make sure. Yeah. So I'm also thinking on my feet with you like local initiatives and local. Yeah. Farming.

I [00:40:44] Um, you think it's good to have like to separate.

P9 [00:40:50] I'm still thinking because this is, this is also a government intervention of course, because there is a lot of EU subsidies and there's a lot of money going from the government towards regular farmers still. And now they're still putting the money to the regular farmers like saying, Oh, okay, so sorry, you have to leave your business and we still give you money. So it's really about, yeah, the investing in the old system and investing in the new system. And I think that was also a separate tipping point as far as I remember.

I [00:41:23] Yeah. But I still will put it, because it's also important to capture the interlinkages. So I will maybe governmental support.

P9 [00:41:33] Because it's needed. I guess you have these local initiatives by themselves that are flourishing already. They are doing it. But then if we want to move faster and on a bigger scale, I think we do need that government money, that public money to go in the right direction.

I [00:41:50] Okay, yeah, maybe something like this. And then the rest is linked to.

P9 [00:41:58] Uh, and yeah, I'm sorry. And to make that really specific with Hachnelook [?], we were also renting land, but we always had to pay for the land to pachters [tenants] or to landlords like rich families like the family van Burningan [? - family's name] and or to even to local government. And actually, we should have gotten money from them because we were making the soil healthy again.

Biodiversity was there. There was food grown in a healthy way. So we were enhancing many things and at the same time we had to pay for the land. And if you work on the land as a regular farmer, you will get on the subsidy and you should even get a higher subsidy if you work in a regenerative way, if you still want to balance that because. So that was quite interesting. It was really hard to make money off the land because um, yeah, it was quite expensive.

I [00:43:02] Yeah. So maybe I put this post-it on the market based incentives, taxation subsidies in the middle seems that it's kind of important. Um, and I think you said a lot of important things. I would try to capture it.

P8 [00:43:21] At the same time, I like to emphasize I do agree, but it is possible to do it without it, it would make, it would support acceleration. But it's not that, it's not impossible. Mm.

P9 [00:43:33] Yeah. It's like you tell us something else.

P8 [00:43:35] Yeah. So it's accelerating. The this the, the possibility for distribution. So for the to enlarge scale in, in this, this distributive way.

P9 [00:43:50] Yeah.

P8 [00:43:51] But it's not that, it's that it's a prerequisite and sometimes that's failed as well because indeed there are so many subsidies for, for farmers as for big oil. But you really get crazy if you had like P9 just shared also and you would get crazy if you think of that. But then still you are able to pull this off, which only shows that, you know, it's maybe obsolete.

I [00:44:19] And what are the interventions that make these things happening without um, without governmental support. So you just mentioned it can happen.

P8 [00:44:29] The example I gave that people are, you know, creating, are creating a ripple effect. And so it goes maybe not that quick, but at the same time, you know, if there are always these examples, if how long it takes when the water dribble is dribbling into a stadium, how long it takes the stadium is filled. I don't know exactly the figures, but actually it goes quite quickly. And this is the same, you know, if, uh, 200 families are enthusiastic and they share and then maybe into other places, there was a new farm. And of course that takes another 1 to 2 years to make it get it started. But, you know, you get this, this ripple effect and it's so I really believe in that, actually.

P9 [00:45:16] I can agree.

I [00:45:19] Nice. Okay.

P8 [00:45:21] And every time indeed when I speak to people, I hear new initiatives in Amsterdam, more initiatives. And probably in the north there are plenty of initiatives where we even haven't heard of yet. So, yeah, we have. We have a little bit Dutch approach on this perspective, but I really see a lot happening here, without even knowing everything.

P9 [00:45:45] Yeah, Yeah, I do. I do bring in also the, I mean this deep transformation network with Jeremy Lens. I don't know if you know Jeremy and there are also people around the globe and they have these same ideas and they work on the same thing. So they, they mostly work with the commons, with the see as a concept like getting local money, getting local initiatives, getting also local politics involved, um, to making sure they have buildings and they have land. Um, so yeah, for other sectors also buildings are important for creating like wood works or play works or, and to have employment for young people who are unemployed in cities where. Yeah. So, so I recognized this pattern also on a global scale. Um.

I [00:46:35] So would you agree that we just put a link from the connections between farmers and communities back to the local initiative so that there is like an a feedback. So from what I got now is that you, um, you're described that it's kind of like this ripple effect. So if we have local initiatives, we wil have more local initiatives, so we have more connections and also from the connections also the initiatives arise in a way. Does it make sense for you? Um, I mean, I will listen to his interview afterwards again and try to make it more explicit, but just for now to, for the three of us to agree on one like a map.

P9 [00:47:18] Yeah I think it works that way like you have here in the area, like there's a couple of farmers who are doing regenerative agriculture and they they are in a kind of a collaboration and then others see it as well. I think it does work that way. Yeah, they joined websites and then others can join on the website to sell their, their food. Yeah. So I do think that they influence each other. And I also heard from a farmer in the north, she says, everybody first said I was crazy, but I did it anyway. And then other farmers will come to her farm and say, What are you actually doing and how are you doing this. S o I think it does work that way.

I [00:48:02] Yeah, perfect. Yeah.

P8 [00:48:04] Also on that on the farmer side, absolutely true. I always recall and it's actually already story from some time ago where there is one farmer, two farmers and, so next to each other and one farmer decides I don't want to go grow, grow, grow. So he starts to diversify. And they're also starting a leading centre and a place where people can come for a drink and he's going to make his own

cheese. And the other farmer decides to grow, grow, grow, in this case, have more cows. And in the end, actually, the first farmer just makes the same profit as the other one in a far more relaxed way. And the farmer who went for grow, grow and got an additional loan, then have a loan and actually feels really unhappy because he doesn't know all the cows anymore. And he's pressed into a position that, you know, this is the only thing you can do because, you know, because of the the contracts he agreed to do. So it's actually not even a financial discussion anymore any longer. It's just, you know, what do you like to do with your life? And yeah, do we want to be part of the solution or part of the problem, and nobody wants to be part of the problem, you know. And more and more people start to realize that that sometimes indeed they are stuck. And because of the contracts and it's not so easy to, to get out. And sometimes people did have the luck that they realized in time and they were able to change it for the better for themselves.

I [00:49:47] So maybe I add a post-it on like personal values, wishes something like this of the farmers, which is important.

P8 [00:49:59] Yeah.

P9 [00:50:01] Yeah. I think that's relevant because as soon as you feel that as somebody who's buying the food, then you get a sense of this is real honest food and somebody who's enthusiastic about the food that does something. It's different than buying it from an anonymous place basically in the supermarkets, you don't know. And of course, the supermarkets try it as well. They put these farmers on their packaging. This is young. This is where the milk comes from. But I don't think that's the same as really knowing where it comes from.

P8 [00:50:36] And also with the farmers I think in the end, they also like to be more connected. So they the things they grow and the food they grow and the animal they they feed. And it's. Yeah, yeah. It's just something that happens in our society. That we now realize that's not going to work. Mm hmm. And not only, actually, on agriculture perspective. From an agriculture perspective as well. So I do believe that there are a lot of social tipping points which are actually assuming the same for any transition or all transitions needed.

I [00:51:25] Okay. So I still have, like, a collection of interventions on the left side. And you can also say that they're not important. That's also just like maybe you have a look at them and say, okay, is it important?

P8 [00:51:39] What I have already said it's slows down, you know, dominance of conventional agricultural institutions, of course, also businesses. It's really slowing slowing down.

I [00:51:51] Okay. So I just. Mm hmm. Yeah, I just. You're right. I mean, dominance of conventional agriculture institutions and lobbying. I think it's similar. So I just like put it together, yeah you are right.

P8 [00:52:06] And also the information campaigns, promotion of healthy lifestyles, of course, you know but if this heigh from five (Dutch expression) that's developed by the Dutch university and government is still promoting you know if every traditional setup of course it would be better if they didn't and because a lot of people don't realize and I don't think that's communicated enough and I'm not sure whether it's the essence, but the realization that like the strawberries I mentioned, you know, when you'll probably want strawberry and and 20 years ago or 30 years ago, I don't know exactly, you probably had more Vitamin C where, you know eat a full plate of strawberries. So from a nutritional value, the food we have been growing in what we now call traditional agricultural, agricultural or conventional agriculture. We only looks at quantity, not on nutritional value. And I think that's really an issue.

I [00:53:23] But would you say that generally information campaigns could accelerate this process?

P8 [00:53:28] I don't believe in campaigns to be honest.

I [00:53:30] Okay. Okay. I mean, that's also.

P8 [00:53:32] But if the dietists are still using a traditional loan of dated, our out of date guideline that should be changed. And so I think for the information campaign.

P9 [00:53:48] One campaign that I did think had some effects like Wakker Dier [<https://www.wakkerdier.nl/campagnes/plofkip/>] they talked about Plofkip [broiler chicken] in Holland.

P8 [00:53:54] Oh, yeah.

P9 [00:53:55] They were really talking about chicken who was fed in a certain way and that's a Plofkip so that it's unhealthy chicken, basically. And it kind of hammered that down for a long time. I think everybody in Holland knows that term.

P8 [00:54:08] It hat it's effect.

P9 [00:54:10] Yeah.

P8 [00:54:11] And chocolate. They also did that before that with chocolate. The chocolate with (incomprehensible - Dutch expression). Yeah. They had a similar same campaign that also worked.

P9 [00:54:19] Yeah. So I'm with you on the like more positive campaign side. So I think that takes a long time if you have to tell people every day, eat your tomato.

P8 [00:54:28] But wake up campaigns can absolutely help.

P9 [00:54:31] Yes. Yes. I actually kind of. Yeah.

P8 [00:54:34] I mean, they've been very successful.

P9 [00:54:38] Yeah. Yeah. So they just continue with the with that. Yeah. Also about the cow milk and the the held the health of small cows et cetera.

I [00:54:50] A documentary also get a lot of good hear [?] like the couch puricy [?] and. Yeah.

P9 [00:54:56] Yeah. I think that's a little bit more in our bubble, I must say. So if you look at more, mass people, they, they, uh, people in mass consumption, I think they kind of hear these things on the radio or they watch television, and then they kind of hear it all the time, like, Oh, Plofkip must be something going on with my chicken. Yeah, if you do it like in a very, you know, repetitive and like. Yeah. It could do something. So if you talk about poison, like, I mean, lots of foods are poisoned by the pesticides. I think that needs a campaign. Okay, but. But who's gonna run it, huh? So I think it's going to be a we need an NGO for that, because, uh, or Greenpeace or.

P8 [00:55:41] Oh yeah. That's maybe a good intervention.

P9 [00:55:44] Yeah. So if you could put it somewhere in there. Because I think if people become aware that the food they eat is actually not healthy, it's actually bad for your health. I think people might want to change.

I [00:55:57] So and you just said, okay, what would be important to mention to have an NGO to to run these campaigns or what?

P9 [00:56:03] I think it's. Yeah, yeah. You need to. It can't be the government telling you because the government will never do that. I mean they're still supporting conventional agricultural, where all these pesticides are used so it should be, you know NGOs.

P8 [00:56:22] I put a link to the campaign that P9 was referring to from Wakker Dier and Plofkip and it's in Dutch. So Google Translate will help you out.

P9 [00:56:33] Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:56:34] And I mean, in general, Dutch is actually if you speak English and German I think. But yeah, it depends.

P8 [00:56:43] Yeah absolutely.

I [00:56:44] Okay that's actually super interesting.

P9 [00:56:46] And there's one other thing about campaigns. I just think out loud. People in Holland kind of tend to say, Oh, it's so expensive. They kind of they really. They don't want to pay for their food. It's either it's different in Germany or in France or Italy. So if we do something about that, I mean, you have these true pricing institutes and there's you know, there's lots of people working on a true price. But how about?

P8 [00:57:11] If you then look for nutritional nutritional value. Yeah, this is completely changed the story. Yes. It's not about volume. It's about, you know, are you getting what you need? And it's not expensive at all.

P9 [00:57:27] Yeah. And the supermarkets are, of course, pushing like volume and they're making that, you know, cheap.

I [00:57:33] Mm hmm.

P9 [00:57:35] Yeah. Well, just.

P8 [00:57:37] And then you can also play there because actually what I will always find stupid. All the time they often used to do that when they had in the weekend this offer, this large supermarket chain. They had then ten buns for the price of eight, but those ten were in weight the same as the regular eight. But it felt like you had more for free. And it's, of course, the same what you can do with for example, high biological maintenance (incomprehensive), because then people will always say it's more expensive because then they will see that they get only two for the price of four. But if you make those to a little bit smaller that you can make four and then you have the same price, only it's less weight. But they still have four pieces of biological of you and it's the same price and okay, then, you know, they are lighter in weight, but you still have four. So it's also sometimes just smart thinking.

I [00:58:38] Mm hmm. Okay. So I've tried to add this. I'm not sure if I succeeded.

P8 [00:58:45] Maybe it's just in the back of your mind.

I [00:58:46] Yeah, but it's still. I mean, as I said, I will listen to everything again.

P9 [00:58:52] And I'm still sorry. New topic again?

I [00:58:55] No, go ahead.

P9 [00:58:56] Lobby against. I mean, I'm still thinking about that because they have such a large impact, for instance, if you want to grow oats you you are obliged to get these seeds from from those companies unless you have your own seeds. And once it's your own seed, you can just reuse it and it starts multiplying. So you have your own seeds and then they can't force you to take it from them every year. But now I've seen already the movements that they also are, and they're of course all very clever people and they also start to offering biological seeds and more like they want to move in this market. Right. And still then farmers will become dependent of these big corporations. For instance, in Flevoland [province in the Netherlands], you have these grain farmers who are now taking their grains from they used to be like a cattle farm with the milk and they they now know, okay, I have to that's going to be a problem because I have to kind of shrink my farm. And now they start growing oats, but they still do it in the conventional way, like with pesticides and with manure with the kunstmist [artificial fertilizer] I don't know the English word, but then they take the grains from also the conventional suppliers, which is actually not I mean, they don't need to do that. They can grow and grow their own grains and have their own, you know, their own seeds. Um, so I'm still kind of worried about these large conventional companies because they still, they still do have a lot of power. Also P8 said about political movements in Holland and I mean that's that shows that we haven't reached a tipping point yet on a larger scale so um so wondering yeah. What their impact still is. Mhm. And also on localisation because, because that's not local food that's coming from like big factories, seed factories and then they grow it on a local level, but it's still not the food we want. But they have these grains for human consumption and they will start to make oat milk, but it's still not healthy oat milk.

I [01:01:08] Yeah, I see.

P9 [01:01:10] Yeah.

I [01:01:12] So in the end, lobbying our conventional agricultural dominance impacts everything. If I understand you correctly? I mean.

P9 [01:01:22] Yeah. And then we might have the transition towards less meat and more plants, which is good. Yeah, but still the nutrition wise and, and biodiversity and the health of the soil is still not what we want.

I [01:01:36] Yeah. Okay.

I [01:01:40] Not sure how to link that now, but maybe I can put a comment.

P9 [01:01:48] Well they still have a negative impact on, um, on the, the real, um. Regenerative agriculture.

I [01:01:58] Mm hmm.

P9 [01:02:00] They want to block it. They're mining potential (incomprehensive) and, uh. Mm hmm. at large scale. And then you could say, um. Yeah. So it has a negative impact.

I [01:02:12] Yeah. So try to capture it quickly. Wow. Okay. No, it's getting.

P9 [01:02:22] And I think that the solution is to counter lobby. You have to. (pause) And it's also done by Herenboeren and all these organisations, they have to get to the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) initiative. And also on Earth Day there was this one man who said if we we need to become even more collective, like with all these different initiatives, we need to connect it. And then we have 400,000 people who we can easily reach to have their signatures on the new convention, and that we push that towards The Hague and it can be done if we want a part of the money that The Hague is now investing, it needs to go. Some of the money needs to go to regenerative agriculture, not only to conventional farmers and to make sure that they can stop their business needs to be moved into the right direction.

I [01:03:22] So if I link know the independent NGOs and the local initiatives to the lobbying, would this kind of capture what you just said? So kind of the cooperation between initiatives and the NGOs around regenerative agriculture, but.

P9 [01:03:41] And I'm not sure if it's my opinion, but but I'm just kind of exploring it because I'm also like P8 I'm kind of a positive person. I think if you all on a local level, do your your business, I think it's can work. But still, if you want to speed it up and get more money for local initiatives, if they are all collectively saying, okay, we are a big, large part of Dutch society, these local initiatives. And yeah, if you want to spend local public money sorry public money, then please also spend it on us.

I [01:04:23] Mm hmm.

P9 [01:04:25] Because all that money is coming from the local people. Yeah.

I [01:04:31] So kind of bring back the taxes of local people to the local. Yeah. Economy.

P9 [01:04:41] Yeah. Don't put it towards FrieslandCampina [multinational company in food industry, <https://www.frieslandcampina.de/de/>] and to the bigger farmers that are connected there. But bring it to bring it to real local food.

P8 [01:04:52] And then, you know, if you start thinking this all through then indeed, I don't want to maybe go too quick into the consequences which are already listed, but in the end they don't need packaging, you don't need transportation. So it also contributes to radically reducing the CO2 emission. It enhances the soil and therefore biodiversity. It's more a healthier food. So it's actually I would add human health as well. So consequences are also linked to energy transition, to climate change, to increasing human health, social cohesion, all the all the big issues of this time. So the consequences sounds a little bit negative, but they are actually meant very positive. I rather would say results.

P9 [01:05:48] Yeah.

P8 [01:05:50] Or outcomes. Yeah, yeah.

P9 [01:05:51] Yeah, yeah.

P8 [01:05:52] So yeah, reducing climate change, reducing carbon emissions and restoring soil and therefore enhancing biodiversity.

I [01:06:05] Mm hmm.

P8 [01:06:06] Social cohesion. So there are so many positive outcomes as well. And it's often, I think where our governments really goes wrong go wrong goes wrong. They don't look it, they don't take this broader approach, you know, because they all have these issues and they all stare at these issues one by one. But actually when you combine them. Yeah. And you really take an in-depth holistic approach, you actually solve all the other ones as well, solve or at least contribute to it. In a positive way.

I [01:06:40] Nice. So I'm going to try to collect like the results that you mentioned. That would, if I understand correctly, and would result from the local initiatives from local farming that enhance regenerative agriculture.

P8 [01:06:53] Also radical CO2 reduction or CO2 reduction, you don't have to call it radical, but uh, because of less transport, you actually don't need packaging the goods. You know, everything goes into a crate when the families have their own. Yeah. So it's ridiculous that you pack a cucumber in plastic to say yeah, then you enhance the the lifetime. Yeah, that's simply the matter of long wrong logistics. You know it's not a cucumber doesn't need plastic to enhance the lifetime you know.

P9 [01:07:29] It's because they transport it from that far (incomprehensible).

P8 [01:07:32] So that's not the right answer. It's not, it's not the right question. Yes, you're right. The problem is the transport. Yeah. Yeah.

I [01:07:43] Yeah. Nice. I mean, I think I won't connect everything now otherwise, I think it will become super messy. But I think we all agree that these results come from. Yeah. So. So local initiatives and. Yeah, nice. I mean, I think we. I'm really happy with what you said. It's helping me a lot. And yeah, maybe we go into a little reflection round, so, um, and I will give you maybe yeah, a few minutes again to go through, like read through this again a bit more carefully and think if anything important, is missing if any link is missing, if you want to highlight something. Um, and also the question, what is really the most important thing in this web. So can you say, okay, this link or this element is really super important, but I can give if you maybe 3 minutes, I'll give you 3 minutes, but. It also try to zoom a little bit.

P9 [01:09:24] I think most important for me is the local initiatives with and then the connection between farmers and community society. I think once farmers start doing that, then things will flourish. So people need to be connected. If people stay in the narrative of, what's that in English, of duality (incomprehensible) and of I need to do it myself. I need to do it alone. And I don't think we move to the next stage. Some connection. And if they can connect with like local supermarkets and local retail, and if they connect to local transportation, for instance. Like in Arnhem [Dutch city], we have local transporters on a bicycle and electric bicycle, and then we have like, that's how they transported the food. So also for people who don't have the time to go to all these farmers, etc., they could get their local fruits delivered by electric bikes. Hmm. And that's again, local employment because people are on these bicycle. And so anything on the local level.

P8 [01:10:39] We can make it even more nicer when you let P9 tell you (incomprehensible).

P9 [01:10:46] They would even transport.

I [01:10:47] I guess, economical. Local stimulation of local economies. You know, that's that's absolutely true. You can safely say.

I [01:10:56] Mm hmm.

P9 [01:10:57] Because I just really like that. Because they said Then we bring food somewhere, but we also transport because we were making beer, for instance, A beer is quite heavy. And then they would transfer the beer to the restaurants and people would come and eat in the local restaurant and they would have the local beer there. So you kind of need that transportation network as well. They only I don't remember their name. I think it's like green green bikes. They were only in a connection in Arnhem and they were exploring also on the local level in different cities. So. Yeah. And then you don't need any transportation with the big trucks, anymore. And on electric vehicles (incomprehensive). Yeah.

I [01:11:38] And maybe again, this question because I'm still. How to start this ripple effect. I think this wonders in my mind. So I understand that we have like local initiatives and connections. It's kind of reinforce that itself. But how if we have like a clean landscape and no local initiatives, how would we start this, um, this ripple effect to happen? How will we start these local initiatives?

P9 [01:12:05] So there is a city or an area where nothing happens yet.

I [01:12:08] Yes.

P9 [01:12:10] How we would get there.

P8 [01:12:11] How would we go there?

I [01:12:12] So what would be what would be measures or interventions that could.

P8 [01:12:18] P9, you already said that personal values or wishes of farmers or or citizens you know as well, because that's actually also how Herenboeren [?] Started. It was like, you know, this is not going to work. You know, this is not healthy. And, you know, we need to connect the people back to the. So there are always individuals that see things have to be different. Mm hmm. And now we already have it, so we don't have to start from scratch. You know, you just can link people. Hey, did you hear of Herenboeren, the Herenboeren farm or the Lenteland farm or Bodemzicht? Can we start something here as well? Or. And let's have a look at and it's it's really great. So there always will be

individuals that have it's it's like, you know, things emerge even have before the times of social media at the same time. So sometimes the time is just ready. And I think that's what it is. The time is now because you know, we are yeah, it's holding this earth and it's it's it's it's reaching its limits. So, you know, and in those kind of situation these Yeah. Rough areas or in these rough situations, then new new initiatives emerge. So it's just a time so you don't have to force it, it just will happen.

I [01:13:45] Okay.

P8 [01:13:47] Yeah. You only what you can do is accelerate it and that's indeed on what's P9 said about governments moving funding from traditional agriculture and fossil to regenerative approaches for example or NGOs for start campaigns. So it will happen. I have no doubts about it. But it needs to happen probably more fast than it's organically will will happen. So, therefore, all the things P9 suggested the are, would be great, but it will happen.

P9 [01:14:29] Yeah. I'm second to all of that, and I think here also to meet people need to be connected. So I, I think like there's this initiative in Holland pushed by Decade of Action and yeah, two days ago there were again there was the family van Burningan [?] Was there. They have a lot of money they have land so and they came to this event of farmers talking about regenerative agriculture. And I met them once because we, we had a presentation of Hachnelook [?]. Because the owner knows the family and you need to kind of connect people because once you bring the money where the knowledge is and the farmers are. And then I think that's that's just very important because we also need the investors and there's also an investor company in that building and they invest in all kinds of sustainability initiatives. So I think making sure you bring people together is really crucial.

I [01:15:32] Yeah, I added like a post-it with networks between initiatives, different stakeholders, connection between different people.

P8 [01:15:39] Van Burningan [?]. Yeah, because they this is a great example for a family, but also our business that really wants, who are actually very socially motivated. You know, it's not that they will drop everything what they are doing because it's not the right way to do it anymore. But they are they are getting into the transition. They say, okay, this is not what we want anymore, so we are going to change our business. And I really had the opportunity to to work with them a number of years back. And then but I really was impressed with, you know, the intention of the company as well. I don't know the family, but but the people working at the company, even (incomprehensive) [name of a company] although they were not always yet on the right track, the willingness to to really change.

P9 [01:16:32] Yeah they're also exploring it I think, yes, they need these big land owners. They need to kind of sustain their property, sustain the house and the family needs to live there. But the family's outgrown the property also. So they also live in cities somewhere else. So they kind of try to find ways to make sure they can invest their money in the right way and still live from it. That's basically what they still aim for. But um, yeah.

I [01:17:01] (incomprehensive) agriforest that I talked about the initiative here is also from, actually supported by a family who also owns lands and forests here, and they had some agricultural fields that were completely depleted. So they actually offered those lands that lands for free to the agriforest initiatives. You know, if we're going to regenerate it, it's perfect for us. And so, yeah, great, they really like to support that initiative. So yeah, that's super cool.

P9 [01:17:34] Yeah, that's super. That was also.

P8 [01:17:35] And those kind of families are everywhere that so yeah, that's.

I [01:17:40] Nice. Yeah, I think we were like 10 minutes left. So I would like to go into like kind of little last questions and feedback round and so it's more of a practical organisational level. So would it be okay for you if you sent me some links and authors and names you mentioned? I mean, I don't know if how much work it is. I don't want to put.

P8 [01:18:06] I already put it in the chat.

I [01:18:08] Okay, nice. So, or if you can think of anything else, it would be really really I think for me it's really nice to have like these information and I'm not sure if I can extract all the names you mentioned from these interviews, but I will try.

P8 [01:18:23] But now you have them in the chat, the one I feel is really important.

P9 [01:18:27] I, you work with Decade of Action or with.

I [01:18:32] Um. Yeah, I work with Decade of Action.

P9 [01:18:34] And the Re-Generation, right? Yeah. Yeah. So I don't need to mention.

I [01:18:37] Yeah. Yeah. Okay. Nice. Perfect. Thank you. I will write them down later. And so I will listen to the interview again and clean the diagram up. And if it would be okay for you, I would send you the diagram again and ask for feedback. And just to make sure that I don't. Yeah. Confused

anything, forgot anything. But yeah, always. Like if you have time. Yeah. I'm really glad about feedback but if not then just let me know.

P8 [01:19:13] We'll do.

P9 [01:19:17] Yeah.

I [01:19:18] And then in the like, my last question is if my last question is if you have any comments or feedback for me, like for the interview in general or for the interview process. So because you're like my second interview now and I have four more that are coming and if you have any suggestions, I mean, I already put results instead of consequences. But yeah, if you have any like comments or suggestions how I could do something differently? Yeah, I'm glad to listen.

P8 [01:19:48] Not from my side for this point, maybe after reflection, but not at this point in time.

I [01:19:53] Yeah. I mean, you always can always send me a message or write me an email. If you can think of anything.

P9 [01:19:58] I thought it was well done. Also because we were talking and you were moving things around. Yeah. Well done, because it's hard to follow and connect.

P8 [01:20:09] And it makes it indeed easier for us because then we just can let our mind flow and think about it because that's what actually hate about Miro if you start to type, you know, if you do this with a post it and write, then it supports your thinking. But if you do this on a computer, it actually it's distract you from thinking. So it was very great that you did this, so that really works. Yeah. No, I would suggest don't ask your interviewees indeed, to do it. This really works, because for me at least it would distract me from thinking.

I [01:20:40] Yeah. I also had the feeling that kind of the post-its work as inspiration, and you just kind of started just like talking. And it was. Yeah, I think it was good. Yeah.

P9 [01:20:52] If I can. Yeah. I have a practical question for you P8. I would like to connect with you, but I don't have your last name, so.

P8 [01:21:00] Yeah. P8. Yeah, I tried to change it, but I fill it in before and do you see the chat uh.

P9 [01:21:10] Yeah, I see the chat.

P8 [01:21:11] Yeah. My name is P8. You can find me on LinkedIn.

P9 [01:21:14] And it's super. Yeah. Yeah.

P8 [01:21:16] Okay. I'm P8.

P9 [01:21:17] Thank you.

P8 [01:21:19] Yeah sorry, I. I just was last minutes.

P9 [01:21:22] It's no problem. Yeah. Yeah.

P8 [01:21:25] Okay. Nice to be connected, because thanks for letting me, let me meet P9, I, because I do. Yeah.

I [01:21:33] Yeah, it's okay. Okay. So. Yeah, thank you very much. And yeah, enjoy your day. Thank you. Goodbye.

P8 [01:21:44] Looking forward to meeting you again one way or another.

P9 [01:21:48] Yes.

P8 [01:21:49] Okay.

I [01:21:50] Nice. Bye. Bye.

P9 [01:21:52] Bye.